

ARTICLE TYPE

On designing transport networks with latency guarantees for next-generation services

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Abstract

This article presents an open-source network simulator and digital twin focused on the analysis of latency in Metropolitan Area Networks (MAN). Our tool can estimate delay percentiles between pairs of nodes, aiming to see if the MAN can support emerging services and applications with strict latency requirements. We show that probability bounds like Vysochanskij–Petunin (VP) inequality can be used to accurately estimate latency percentiles between pairs of nodes with minimal computational effort. Theoretical results are validated with extensive simulations leveraging the *simmer* package, an open-source Discrete Event Simulator (DES) written in R, along with *igraph* for visualization of networks and shortest path calculations. Two versions of the simulator are provided as open-source in Github for the research community to use and build upon: one for local PC and a second one optimized to be executed in the cloud with multiple cores and massive memory.

KEYWORDS:

Latency percentiles; Queuing models; Probabilistic inequalities; Vysochanskij–Petunin inequality.

1 | INTRODUCTION

According to ITU-T FGNET 2030, the forthcoming next-generation networks envisioned for 2030 will require important upgrades in five dimensions: Bandwidth, Time, Security, AI, and Manynets¹. Such upgrades are necessary to give support to foreseen upcoming use cases and services, namely Holographic type communications (HTC), Tactile Internet for remote operations (TIRO), Intelligent operation network (ION), Network and computing convergence (NCC), Digital twin (DT), Space-terrestrial integrated network (STIN) and Industrial IoT (IIoT) with cloudification.

These seven use cases are expected to require bandwidth upgrades and latency reductions from the network, especially in the Metropolitan Area Network (MAN); in particular, HTC, TIRO and DT will demand both high-bandwidth and low-latency communications between the access node (or Access Central Office, ACO) close to the user and the MAN nodes where computing and storage resources are allocated (typically, a Regional or National Central Office^{2,3,4}). Essentially, the Time dimension foreseen by FGNET-2030 comprises important innovations in the network to reduce latency and jitter and improve synchronization and accuracy along with scheduling coordination and geolocation.

Bandwidth capacity has been increasing over the years at a steady pace, as can be seen from the evolution of Ethernet standards, going from 100M Fast Ethernet in 1995 (IEEE 802.3u⁵) to 200G, 400G and 800G Ethernet (IEEE 802.3bs⁶ and⁷). Moreover, 1.6 TbE and 3.2 TbE are expected to become a standard shortly (IEEE P802.3dj study group⁸). Improved bandwidth goes hand-in-hand with reduced latency, as it results from queuing theory^{9,10}.

In general, applications and services have different tolerance to latency and jitter. For instance, emerging services such as Connected Industry, Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X), extended reality, or digital twins will demand even more strict delay guarantees to properly operate (e.g. latency values below 10 ms, even 1 ms, in virtual reality, telesurgery or Tactile Internet)^{11,12,13}. Pervious¹⁴ briefly overview 3GPP TS22.261 maximum end-to-end delay requirements for different 5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) services like split control for robotics (12 ms), gaming (10 ms), virtual reality (5-10 ms) and Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) image recognition (1 ms).

The total latency experienced by an IP packet includes all those components introduced by the different network segments and the processing delay at the computation elements at the network edge or cloud. The first part is often referred to as the transport latency, the delay perceived by a packet as it travels through the network infrastructure. However, the application's latency perceived by the user not only depends on the network infrastructure and its capacity and throughput but also the protocol stack running below the application layer, typically TCP/IP. A good overview of all sources of latency can be found in the literature¹⁵.

Concerning transport latency, a TCP/IP network has four main latency sources: propagation, processing, transmission, and queuing¹⁶. Propagation delay only depends on the distance traveled by the electrical or optical signal divided by their speed on that particular media, i.e. 300,000 km/s for air or 200,000 km/s for silica fiber or cable; this translates into 3.33 $\mu\text{s}/\text{km}$ and 5 $\mu\text{s}/\text{km}$ respectively. Recently, the research community has proposed prototypes of hollow-core fibers (HCF) where light propagates at a speed that approaches 300,000 km/s, like over the air and with even smaller attenuation to silica fibers^{17,18,19}.

Processing delay at intermediate nodes involves packet header lookup, Time-To-Live (TTL) decrease, checksum and/or CRC verification, Forward Error Correction (FEC) processes, etc. This has been reducing over time to less than 1 μs per hop, about 300 ns²⁰. Finally, concerning transmission and queuing delay, this has been exhaustively studied by the research community over the years^{21,22}. A good overview of recently measured Round-Trip Time (RTT) delays (pings) over different monitoring stations across the globe can be found in the literature²³.

In general, the majority of services travel from the end users to the Content Delivery Network (CDN) in the Metro segment (where storage and computing resources are available, along with cached contents) or to the core nodes interfacing the Wide Area Network (WAN)^{2,24,3}. The MAN segments are thus necessary to provide sufficient bandwidth capacity to move the traffic flows from the users to the data centers and WAN nodes, while satisfying strict latency restrictions, especially for real-time services. To this end, the network operators must monitor their network continuously and guarantee that service requirements are always fulfilled. This includes monitorization of node activity and link load along with latency estimates between pairs of nodes. This has led to the design of Network Digital Twins that provide, in real-time, accurate overviews of the network performance²⁵.

The goal of this article is thus twofold: (1) it describes a Network Digital Twin based on open-source libraries for simulating network delays between nodes in Metropolitan Area Networks (MANs), with an easy-to-use interface that reads inputs and writes outputs to excel files in a simple format; and (2) it provides accurate theoretical latency bounds between nodes with minimal computational effort.

There exist already other popular network simulators available in the literature, some of them can be used as digital twins that accurately represent network status, see for instance ns-3, OMNET++, OPNET and QualNet^{26,27,28,29,30}. However, OPNET and QualNet are not open-source³¹. While NS-3 is primarily supported on Linux, with only limited functionality available for Windows, making it less versatile in cross-platform environments. On the other hand, OMNeT++ offers complex features and configurations that can lead to a steep learning curve for new users requiring significant time and expertise to utilize effectively.

Lightweight packet-based tools built on R and Python are highly suitable for simpler or more focused queuing analysis and simulation^{32,33}. In addition, R's *reticulate* library enables smooth integration of R and Python code, facilitating the use of advanced capabilities from both ecosystems. This integration allows the simulator to interface with powerful R and Python libraries such as *scikit-learn* and *keras* for machine learning, *langchain* for working with large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT or Gemini, and advanced visualization tools such as R's *shiny*³⁴. Furthermore, R and Python code can be run in the cloud, for instance on Google Colab, where multiple CPU cores, memory, and even GPU hardware are available at moderate costs³⁵.

The simulator used in this study, developed using R, not only takes advantage of existing open-source libraries but also enhances user accessibility. It allows users to conveniently input topology information (nodes and links) and traffic matrices via a spreadsheet and generates results in the same format, simplifying the workflow for analysis and interpretation. Our tool is designed to simulate and analyze delay percentiles, that is, the values of delay such that a large majority of the packets are below that percentile value (for instance 99% of them). Although there are well-known formulas to calculate the average latency, analyzing delay percentiles (e.g. 99-th) is interesting to ensure that most of the packets are below a required latency threshold (not just the average). To offer the needed background, we include an overview of the theoretical aspects from a queuing theory

performance perspective and provide simulations within the context of Metro Area Networks (MANs). We show that when MAN networks upgrade to 100 Gb/s and beyond, a large majority of the packets can be bounded below 1 ms within the MAN, also in scenarios of high-burstiness.

It is worth noting that our simulation focuses on the MAN and does not model the access network segment, like Fiber-To-The-Premises (FTTx) technologies like GPON, XGS-PON, or TWDM-PON and their MAC protocols, which have an impact on access latency (both upstream and downstream). This has been addressed in other studies like³⁶.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a quick theoretical background on classical queuing models and probabilistic bounds; Section 3 overviews the scenarios, topologies and simulations conducted together with the results obtained. Section 4 concludes this work with a summary of its main findings and future work.

2 | THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND STATE OF THE ART

2.1 | Transport latency fundamentals

Internet delay has a major impact on the quality of service perceived by users running different applications. Indeed, TCP performance is heavily affected by the Round-Trip Time (RTT) as it follows from the well-known Mathis formula^{37,38}:

$$\text{TCP Throughput} \sim \frac{MSS}{RTT \sqrt{p_{loss}}} \quad (1)$$

where MSS is the Maximum Segment Size, RTT is the two-way end-to-end round-trip time, and p_{loss} is the packet loss probability, due to any factor (packet corruption, collisions in shared media, or buffer overflow due to congestion).

However, as previously stated, RTT is mainly driven by the propagation delay of signals over the transmission media and the bandwidth capacity and load of intermediate routers and switches. Increased bandwidth capacity has a double effect on the network: (1) it allows to move more quantity of traffic from one side of the network to another end, and (2) bits (and therefore packets) are transmitted faster over the physical media.

To illustrate this, consider the following **numerical example**: Two nodes operating at 10 Gb/s separated by a 1 km fiber link. In this case, we should expect the following latency components:

- Propagation delay: 5 μs for silica fiber or 3.33 μs for hollow-core fiber.
- Processing delay: hundreds of nanoseconds per IP node, up to a few microseconds²⁰.
- Transmission delay: 51.2 ns for a 64-Byte packet or 1.2 μs for a 1500-Byte packet.
- Queuing (Waiting) delay: One packet ahead in the queue on average if the link load is 50% load or three packets ahead if the link load is 75% (that is, the link carries 5 Gb/s or 7.5 Gb/s of traffic).

If the link is upgraded to 100 Gb/s, the transmission delay reduces by a factor of 10x, and the queuing delay also reduces since the link load becomes 5% or 7.5% (10x reduction). Hence, when links are upgraded in capacity, there is a boost in network performance from two sides: first, the link can carry much more traffic than in the previous case, and second, the transmission and queuing delay greatly reduces, since packets depart more quickly from the nodes.

The next section briefly reviews state-of-the-art queuing theory for network performance analysis.

2.2 | Single node M/M/1 review

Consider an M/M/1 queuing system, where packet arrivals follow a Poisson process with rate λ packet/s and service times are exponentially distributed with mean $E(X) = \frac{1}{\mu}$. Remark that in exponentially distributed random variables, X characterized by some rate μ , its Probability Density Function (PDF) follows:

$$f_X(t) = \mu e^{-\mu t}, \quad t \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

and its expectation and standard deviation are both equal to:

$$E(X) = \frac{1}{\mu} = Sd(X) \quad (3)$$

and therefore its squared coefficient of variation, computed as variance divided by squared mean is:

$$C_x^2 = \frac{Var(X)}{[E(X)]^2} = \frac{\frac{1}{\mu^2}}{\left(\frac{1}{\mu}\right)^2} = 1 \quad (4)$$

In addition, the second moment $E(X^2)$ can be obtained as:

$$E(X^2) = Var(X) + [E(X)]^2 = \frac{2}{\mu} \quad (5)$$

Following the M/M/1 queuing model, where packet arrivals follow a Poisson process with intensity/rate λ packet/s and service times are exponentially distributed with service rate μ packet/s ($\lambda < \mu$), the delay D experienced by a packet chosen at random in a node (including only transmission and queuing, not propagation) follows an exponential distribution whose Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) is:

$$F_D(t) = 1 - e^{-\frac{t}{E(D)}}, \quad t \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

where the mean delay $E(D)$ is given by:

$$E(D) = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - \rho} = \frac{1}{\mu - \lambda} \quad (7)$$

Also $S_d(D) = \frac{1}{\mu - \lambda}$ for the exponential distribution. Here, $\rho = \frac{\lambda}{\mu} < 1$ is the so-called link load, i.e. the ratio between packet arrival rate and packet service rate.

The CDF of D further allows to find any delay percentile D_p , that is, the value such that p percentage of the packets experience a delay of D_p or less. In other words, the value of D_p that guarantees:

$$F_D(t \leq D_p) = p = 1 - e^{-\frac{D_p}{E(D)}} \quad (8)$$

Using simple algebra allows us to find the value of the p -th delay percentile D_p as:

$$D_p = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - \rho} \ln \left(\frac{1}{1 - F_D(t \leq D_p)} \right) \quad (9)$$

Numerical Example: Consider a 10 Gb/s link where packet service times follow an exponential distribution with a mean of $1 \mu s$ (i.e. 10,000-bit packets or 1250 B transmitted over a 10 Gb/s link) and its link load is 75% (i.e. $\rho = 0.75$). In such a case, the average total delay (including transmission and queuing, not propagation) is then:

$$E(D) = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - 0.75} = 4E(X) = 4 \mu s \quad (10)$$

The average total latency is 4x the average service time, that is $4 \mu s$, which includes transmission ($1 \mu s$) and average queuing delay ($3 \mu s$, about 3 average packets ahead in the queue).

To measure how the network behaves on the majority of packets, we are also interested in finding the following high delay percentiles, that is, the latency values such that most packets are below them:

$$D_{.90} = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - 0.75} \ln \frac{1}{1 - 0.9} = 4 \cdot E(X) \cdot 2.3 = 9.2 \mu s \quad (11)$$

$$D_{.99} = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - 0.75} \ln \frac{1}{1 - 0.99} = 4 \cdot E(X) \cdot 4.6 = 18.4 \mu s \quad (12)$$

$$D_{.999} = E(X) \frac{1}{1 - 0.75} \ln \frac{1}{1 - 0.999} = 4 \cdot E(X) \cdot 6.9 = 27.6 \mu s \quad (13)$$

In summary, packets traversing the previous link experience an average delay from input to output of $4 \mu s$ on average (some packets less than that, others more than that); further we can guarantee that almost all of them (99% of them) show a delay of at most $18.4 \mu s$; in other words, only one packet every 100 shows a delay value above $18.4 \mu s$. Thus, delay percentiles give us information about how most packets behave in terms of delay.

Hence, in M/M/1 queuing systems, finding a high-delay percentile like $D_{.99}$ only requires to multiply the average service time $E(X)$ of a packet by the link's load factor $\frac{1}{1-\rho}$ and then take that value and multiply by roughly 5 times to obtain the 99% percentile $D_{.99}$ (or roughly 7x for the 99.9% delay percentile). To further include propagation and processing delay, $5 \mu s$ per kilometer of silica fiber needs to be added to the previous queuing and transmission delay, plus another 0.5 to $1 \mu s$ typically for electronic processing of the packet at every IP node.

The M/M/1 queuing model has been exhaustively studied in the literature and provides closed-form solutions that can be used as a first approach to analyze network performance⁹. However, traffic in real packet-switched networks is better characterized by M/G/1 queuing models, as shown next.

2.3 | Single node M/G/1 review

In the early 1990s, traffic was found to exhibit self-similarity and long-range dependence in both LAN and WAN scenarios^{39,40,41}. The author in⁴² proposed the use of Fractional Brownian Motion (FBM) models to better capture self-similarity and long-range dependence, showing that queuing delays could be better characterized with a Weibull distribution, instead of an exponential one^{43,44}.

However, a decade later (between 2004 and 2009), more experiments with updated measurements revealed that traffic shows Poissonian behavior at the packet time scale (below 100 ms) and self-similarity at higher time scales, in the order of seconds and minutes⁴⁵. Indeed, the authors in⁴⁵ demonstrated that traffic can be characterized by a non-homogeneous Poisson process where inter-arrival times of packets follow an exponential distribution (thus Poisson process) with rate λ packet/s but this rate varies over time.

In such a case, M/G/1 queuing models could be used in scenarios with aggregated traffic from multiple independent traffic sources, like in MAN or WAN scenarios with traffic aggregated from tens of thousands of flows coming from thousands of individual and uncorrelated users. The results of⁴⁵ were found on real traffic traces collected from an OC48 link operating at 2.5 Gb/s. Furthermore, telco networks today aggregate the traffic of multiple sources (thousands of fixed residential households, mobile base stations, and fixed business lines) and operate at bitrates between 10 Gb/s and 100 Gb/s^{46,24} in the Metro segment, and at speeds between 100 or 400 Gb/s in the WAN segment. Soon, networks will be upgraded with newer 800 Gb/s, 1.6 Tb/s, and 3.2 Tb/s transceivers.

Also, the authors in⁴⁷ observed Poisson behavior at small time scales in 2009. A similar trend has been observed recently in memory access behavior⁴⁸, where the level of aggregation of independent sources has increased so much in the last decades and inter-arrival times can be approximated by an exponential distribution (ergo Poisson process).

In this sense, M/G/1 queuing models provide a precise framework for estimating the average queuing delay $E(W_q)$ as it follows from the Pollaczek-Khintchine formula:

$$E(W_q) = \frac{\lambda E(X^2)}{2(1-\rho)} = E(X) \frac{\rho}{1-\rho} \frac{1+C_X^2}{2} \quad (14)$$

where $E(X^2)$ is the second moment of the packet service times and can be obtained as: $E(X^2) = Var(X) + [E(X)]^2 = [E(X)]^2(1+C_X^2)$. The total average latency $E(D)$ requires adding service time, as follows:

$$E(D) = E(X) + E(W_q) \quad (15)$$

It is finally worth noting that, as $\rho \rightarrow 1$, any queuing system with arbitrary inter-arrival times for packets and generic service times approximates an exponential distribution with the following average waiting time in queue (see Kingman's approximation for G/G/1 queuing models²¹):

$$E(W_q) \approx E(X) \frac{\rho}{1-\rho} \frac{C_A^2 + C_X^2}{2}, \quad \text{when } \rho \rightarrow 1 \quad (16)$$

where C_A^2 and C_X^2 are the coefficients of variation of the packet arrival and service times respectively.

It is interesting to remark that the coefficient of variation of packet arrivals for Poisson traffic is $C_A^2 = 1$; furthermore, $C_X^2 = 1.3$ for packet service times as observed at AMS-IX (Amsterdam Internet Exchange¹), where the average packet size of traffic traversed is 1019 Bytes and its standard deviation is 1162 Bytes.

2.4 | Latency bounds for M/M/1 traffic

For any random variable X with finite mean and variance, there exist multiple inequalities that can be used to find upper bounds. Some of the most widely known ones are the Markov, Chebychev, and Vysochanskij–Petunin (VP) inequalities shown below:

¹See Amsterdam Internet Exchange Ethernet Frame Size Distribution, statistics available online at <https://stats.ams-ix.net/sflow/size.html>, accessed on June 2023

$$P(X \geq kE(X)) \leq \frac{1}{k}, \quad \text{Markov's inequality} \quad (17)$$

$$P(|X - E(X)| \geq kSd(X)) \leq \frac{1}{k^2}, \quad \text{Chebychev's inequality} \quad (18)$$

$$P(X - E(X) \geq k \cdot Sd(X)) \leq \frac{4/9}{k^2}, \quad \text{for } k > \sqrt{\frac{8}{3}} \approx 1.633 \quad \text{Vysochanskij-Petunin's inequality} \quad (19)$$

The Vysochanskij-Petunin (VP) inequality also requires that the distribution is unimodal in the sense that there is only a single highest value (or mode).

As a numerical example, consider an M/M/1 queue operating at 10 Gb/s whose average packet service time is 1 μs and server load is 75%. It is worth remarking that, in this scenario, the total delay D follows an exponential distribution whose mean is characterized by Eq. 7; in this case, both average delay and standard deviation are $E(D) = Sd(D) = 4\mu s$ as shown in previous numerical examples.

Then, Markov's inequality guarantees that the 99-th percentile is below $100 \cdot E(D) = 400 \mu s$ as it follows from:

$$P(D \geq 100 \cdot 4 \mu s) \leq \frac{1}{100} = 0.01 = 1 - 0.99$$

Similarly, Chebychev's inequality guarantees that the 99-th percentile is below $10 \cdot Sd(D) + E(D) = 44 \mu s$ since:

$$P(|D - 4 \mu s| \geq 10 \cdot 4 \mu s) \leq \frac{1}{100} = 0.01 = 1 - 0.99$$

Finally, Vysochanskij-Petunin's (VP) inequality, guarantees that the 99-th percentile is below $10\sqrt{4/9} \cdot 4 \mu s + 4\mu s = 30.67 \mu s$ since:

$$P\left(D - 4 \mu s \geq 10\sqrt{4/9} \cdot 4 \mu s\right) \leq \frac{4/9}{\left(10\sqrt{4/9}\right)^2} = 0.01 = 1 - 0.99$$

From Eq. 19, we observe that the VP inequality guarantees an upper bound for the p -th delay percentile of any queuing system as:

$$D_p \leq \sqrt{\frac{4}{9} \frac{1}{1-p}} Sd(D) + E(D) \quad (20)$$

Following eq. 9, the exact true 99-th percentile for an M/M/1 queue is:

$$D_{0.99} = 4 \mu s \frac{1}{1-0.75} \ln \frac{1}{1-0.99} = 18.4 \mu s$$

which is much smaller than the VP inequality of 30.67 μs .

In the following, we review how to use these bounds in an end-to-end scenario where packets must traverse paths with multiple queues in series.

2.5 | Latency bounds in end-to-end paths with multiple hops

Concerning packets traversing multiple hops, the end-to-end delay D_{e2e} experienced by a packet is equal to the sum of the individual delays traversing each intermediate queuing system D_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots$, that is:

$$D_{e2e} = D_1 + \dots + D_N \quad (21)$$

where each D_i represents the total delay at traversing node i (remark that D_i includes queuing and service delay, but not propagation delay).

Since the expectation operator is linear, then the average total delay is the sum of individual expected delays:

$$E(D_{e2e}) = E(D_1) + \dots + E(D_N) = \sum_{i=1}^N E(D_i) \quad (22)$$

In addition, if the D_i random variables are independent, then the total variance is also the sum of individual variance values:

$$Var(D_{e2e}) = Var(D_1) + \dots + Var(D_N) = \sum_{i=1}^N Var(D_i) \quad (23)$$

and its standard deviation is thus: $Sd(D_{e2e}) = \sqrt{Var(D_{e2e})}$

FIGURE 1 (top) Illustration depicting delay simulation for a three-hop path, (bottom) resulting PDF from the simulation for M/M/1 (left) and M/G/1 (right), accompanied by the corresponding theoretical average delay, 99-th percentile, and Vysochanskij–Petunin’s inequality

FIGURE 1 shows an end-to-end path where packets must traverse three 10 Gb/s links with different load values, $\rho_1 = 0.3$, $\rho_2 = 0.5$, and $\rho_3 = 0.4$, alongside a service time of $E(X) = \frac{8 \cdot 1019 \text{ b}}{10 \text{ Gb/s}} = 0.815 \mu\text{s}$, respectively. As shown in the figure, the delay distribution is not analytically tractable, but we observe that the tail looks exponential and similar to the M/M/1 case.

In the M/M/1 case, we can compute both mean and standard deviation of delays D_i per node as in eq. 7:

$$E(D_1) = Sd(D_1) = 0.815 \mu\text{s} \frac{1}{1 - 0.3} = 1.16 \mu\text{s} \quad (24)$$

$$E(D_2) = Sd(D_2) = 0.815 \mu\text{s} \frac{1}{1 - 0.5} = 1.63 \mu\text{s} \quad (25)$$

$$E(D_3) = Sd(D_3) = 0.815 \mu\text{s} \frac{1}{1 - 0.4} = 1.36 \mu\text{s} \quad (26)$$

Hence, the end-to-end delay is:

$$E(D_{e2e}) = E(D_1) + E(D_2) + E(D_3) = 4.15 \mu\text{s} \quad (27)$$

$$Sd(D_{e2e}) = \sqrt{Sd(D_1)^2 + Sd(D_2)^2 + Sd(D_3)^2} = 2.41 \mu\text{s} \quad (28)$$

and the resulting 90-th and 99-th delay percentiles, according to the Vysochanskij–Petunin’s inequality, should be below the following upper bounds:

$$D_{.90} \leq \sqrt{\frac{4}{9} \frac{1}{1 - 0.9}} \times Sd(D_{e2e}) + E(D_{e2e}) = 9.23 \mu\text{s} \quad (29)$$

$$D_{.99} \leq \sqrt{\frac{4}{9} \frac{1}{1 - 0.99}} \times Sd(D_{e2e}) + E(D_{e2e}) = 20.21 \mu\text{s} \quad (30)$$

This theoretical example will be further validated with simulations in the next section.

3 | SIMULATIONS ON MESHED NETWORK TOPOLOGIES

3.1 | MAN scenarios and Simulations setup

This section briefly overviews how to compute delay bounds for each source-destination pair in a given network topology. We shall use the well-known Metropolitan Area Network (MAN) topologies of Milano, Tokyo, and MAN157 used in^{49,50,51} and depicted in **FIGURE 2** .

FIGURE 2 MAN topologies for simulation and evaluation: Milano, Tokyo, and MAN157

For simplicity, both MAN topologies are considered to be hierarchical with two levels: Access Central Offices (ACO) depicted as red nodes: ACOs are closely located to end users (households, mobile base stations, and business leased lines) for collecting their traffic and forward it to the next hierarchical Metro-Aggregation Central Office (MCO) node in the topology (yellow nodes), where services are located (CDN, Video on Demand, Data-center, VNFs, etc) or interconnection with WAN. Thus, each ACO node in the figure is assumed to be a Central Office (CO) collecting traffic from Residential, Mobile, and Business traffic generators. As such, each node is characterized by the number of fixed broadband house-holds (FTTx or xDSL connections), 4G/5G mobile base stations, and dedicated point-to-point connections rented to individual businesses and companies, leading to a final traffic demand offered by the node. The destination node is the closest MCO node for each ACO.

3.2 | Simulation environment

To validate the accuracy of VP bounds in large MAN topologies (like Milano, Tokyo, MAN157), we crafted our simulator using open-source programming language R and some open-source R-libraries: (1) *igraph* for handling and manipulating graphs and networks; and (2) *simmer*, a discrete-event simulator (DES) for analyzing packet delays as they traverse networks of queues; both very powerful tools for simulating networking scenarios as shown in^{33,52}. Our simulator is open-source and can be downloaded from Github⁵³ for the interested reader to use it in his/her scenarios.

FIGURE 3 Simulation environment: *igraph* and *simmer* as core processing tools receiving network topology and traffic matrix as input and returning delay metrics between each pair of nodes as output.

FIGURE 3 shows a schematic view of our simulator. The simulator first takes the topology information (nodes and links) together with the traffic matrix and link capacities, generates an internal representation of the topology and calculates the traffic traversing each link (using the shortest path algorithm for routing) and the associated load on each network link. The *igraph* library is used in this step. The second step calculates different latency metrics (e.g. theoretical and simulated delays, along with their mean and percentiles) at each queue and also end-to-end for each source-destination pair. To do so, we use the *simmer* library for generating individual packets, forwarding them through each path, and collecting their statistics. This allows us to verify whether or not the theoretical equations are valid and how close the latency bounds are to any simulated delay percentiles. The simulator then outputs the metrics of interest which are written back to a Comma-Separated Value (CSV) file for post-processing and visualization.

FIGURE 1 shows an example of the resulting end-to-end delay for the end-to-end scenario described in Section 2.5, after a simulation with 1,000 packets conducted with *simmer*. The average delay is calculated as the sum of individual average delays on each hop (both theoretically and simulated using *simmer*) for M/M/1 and M/G/1 queuing model. As shown, both simulated and theoretical average delays perfectly match. In addition, the figure shows the simulated 99th delay percentile and the result after applying Vysochanskij–Petunin’s inequality formula (eq. 19) for these three links. It is worth noticing that Vysochanskij–Petunin’s inequality is a loose upper bound of the real 99th percentile obtained from the simulation, approximately twice the real value.

3.3 | Validation of latency bounds with simulations

In this section, we evaluate the accuracy of the latency bounds on a subset of end-to-end paths for the Tokyo topology of **FIGURE 2**. Packet simulations take a long time, therefore only a few selected end-to-end paths have been used for validating the equations. These are shown in **TABLE 1** where the rows and columns represent each end-to-end path’s source and destination nodes, respectively. The table shows the average theoretical delays and average simulated ones along with the 99-the simulation percentiles and theoretical VP-bounds for such percentile. In this table, propagation delay is not included to better validate theoretical and simulated values.

As shown in **TABLE 1**, the average delays (first and second rows for every path) perfectly match for every source-destination pair, since both theoretical (based on M/G/1 equations) and simulated packet delays are very close together. For example, for

TABLE 1 End-to-end delay from each ACO to each MCO, WITHOUT PROPAGATION DELAY (in μs)

node N		Tk_02	Tk_03	Tk_06	Tk_07	Tk_08	Tk_09	Tk_10	Tk_11	Tk_12
Tk_01	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	0.07	0.07	0.07	1.41	1.41	1.41	2.75	2.75	3.29
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.07	0.07	0.07	1.25	1.25	1.25	2.50	2.50	3.02
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.33	0.33	0.33	6.16	6.16	6.16	8.80	8.80	10.35
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	0.57	0.57	0.57	10.35	10.35	10.35	15.39	15.39	18.65
Tk_04	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	0.15	0.15	0.15	1.49	1.49	1.95	1.95	3.29	1.95
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.14	0.14	0.14	1.35	1.35	1.76	1.76	3.01	1.76
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.48	0.48	0.48	5.95	5.95	8.38	8.38	10.37	8.38
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	0.85	0.85	0.85	10.44	10.44	14.46	14.46	18.65	14.46
Tk_05	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	0.15	0.15	0.15	1.49	1.49	1.49	2.02	2.83	2.02
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.14	0.14	0.14	1.35	1.35	1.35	1.83	2.55	1.82
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.48	0.48	0.48	5.95	5.95	5.95	8.02	8.70	8.02
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	0.85	0.85	0.85	10.44	10.44	10.44	14.54	15.47	14.54

(a)

node N		Tk_13	Tk_14	Tk_15	Tk_16	Tk_17	Tk_18	Tk_19	Tk_20	Tk_21
Tk_01	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	1.41	0.15	1.49	0.15	2.02	0.15	2.02	1.49	3.29
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	1.25	0.14	1.35	0.14	1.82	0.14	1.82	1.35	3.03
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	6.16	0.48	5.95	0.48	8.02	0.48	8.02	5.95	10.35
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	10.35	0.85	10.44	0.85	14.54	0.85	14.54	10.44	18.65
Tk_04	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	0.07	0.07	1.41	0.07	1.95	0.15	1.95	1.41	1.49
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.07	0.07	1.25	0.07	1.76	0.14	1.76	1.25	1.35
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.33	0.33	6.16	0.33	8.38	0.48	8.38	6.16	5.95
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	0.57	0.57	10.35	0.57	14.46	0.85	14.46	10.35	10.44
Tk_05	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	0.15	0.15	1.49	0.07	1.95	0.07	1.95	1.95	1.41
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.14	0.14	1.35	0.07	1.76	0.07	1.76	1.76	1.25
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	0.48	0.48	5.95	0.33	8.38	0.33	8.38	8.38	6.16
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	0.85	0.85	10.44	0.57	14.46	0.57	14.46	14.46	10.35

(b)

path Tok_01 - Tok_12, the theoretical average delay is 3.29 μs while the simulated value is 3.02 μs . Concerning the 99th percentile in this case, the theoretical bound obtained by the VP equation gives a 99th percentile value of 18.65 μs while the actual percentile value (measured from the simulations) is 10.35 μs . We observe the same trend in all end-to-end paths, that is both simulated and theoretical delays are close together, and the Vysochanskij–Petunin’s bound for 99-th percentiles is about double that of the simulated ones, acting as an upper bound.

TABLE 2 is similar to **TABLE 1**, but now propagation delay is also included in the final results. As shown, most of the delay is due to propagation since at 10 Gb/s and short distances the majority of delay is due to propagation delay. It is interesting to observe that when propagation delay is included, the Vysochanskij–Petunin’s bound is even closer to the simulated delay (third and fourth rows for every source node).

3.4 | Performance evaluation of the simulator

To demonstrate the simulation performance, we first evaluated the running time and memory usage on a local PC equipped with an Intel i7 processor and 16 GB RAM for the three different topologies. We tested each for 1,000, 10,000, and 100,000 packet events per source-destination pair.

TABLE 2 End-to-end delay from each ACO to each MCO, WITH PROPAGATION DELAY (in μs)

node N		Tk_02	Tk_03	Tk_06	Tk_07	Tk_08	Tk_09	Tk_10	Tk_11	Tk_12
Tk_01	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	5.07	5.07	4.07	9.41	11.41	11.41	17.75	17.75	17.29
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	5.07	5.07	4.07	9.25	11.25	11.25	17.50	17.50	17.02
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	5.33	5.33	4.33	14.16	16.16	16.16	23.80	23.80	24.35
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	5.57	5.57	4.57	18.35	20.35	20.35	30.39	30.39	32.65
Tk_04	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	9.15	9.15	8.15	13.49	15.49	10.95	9.95	17.29	9.95
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	9.14	9.14	8.14	13.35	15.35	10.76	9.76	17.01	9.76
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	9.48	9.48	8.48	17.95	19.95	17.38	16.38	24.37	16.38
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	9.85	9.85	8.85	22.44	24.44	23.46	22.46	32.65	22.46
Tk_05	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	9.15	9.15	8.15	13.49	15.49	15.49	13.02	21.83	13.02
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	9.14	9.14	8.14	13.35	15.35	15.35	12.82	21.55	12.82
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	9.48	9.48	8.48	17.95	19.95	19.95	19.02	27.70	19.02
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	9.85	9.85	8.85	22.44	24.44	24.44	25.54	34.47	25.54

(a)

node N		Tk_13	Tk_14	Tk_15	Tk_16	Tk_17	Tk_18	Tk_19	Tk_20	Tk_21
Tk_01	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	11.41	7.15	11.49	7.15	11.02	7.15	11.02	11.49	15.29
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	11.25	7.14	11.35	7.14	10.82	7.14	10.82	11.35	15.03
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	16.16	7.48	15.95	7.48	17.02	7.48	17.02	15.95	22.35
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	20.35	7.85	20.44	7.85	23.54	7.85	23.54	20.44	30.65
Tk_04	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	4.07	3.07	7.41	3.07	6.94	6.15	6.95	7.41	10.49
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	4.07	3.07	7.25	3.07	6.76	6.14	6.76	7.25	10.35
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	4.33	3.33	12.16	3.33	13.38	6.48	13.38	12.16	14.95
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	4.57	3.57	16.35	3.57	19.46	6.85	19.46	16.35	19.44
Tk_05	$\overline{D}^{theor} (\mu s)$	7.15	6.15	10.49	3.07	6.95	3.07	6.95	6.95	7.41
	$\overline{D}^{sim} (\mu s)$	7.14	6.14	10.35	3.07	6.76	3.07	6.76	6.76	7.25
	$D_{99}^{sim} (\mu s)$	7.48	6.48	14.95	3.33	13.38	3.33	13.38	13.38	12.16
	$D_{99}^{VPbound} (\mu s)$	7.85	6.85	19.44	3.57	19.46	3.57	19.46	19.46	16.35

(b)

TABLE 3 Running Time on local PC

Simulation Time	1,000p	10,000p	100,000p
Tokyo (23 nodes)	11 s	55 s	8 min 15 s
Milano (52 nodes)	11 s	27 s	2 min 54 s
MAN157 (157 nodes)	57 s	2 min 7 s	13 min 12 s

TABLE 4 Memory Usage on local PC

Memory	1,000p	10,000p	100,000p
Tokyo (23 nodes)	0.3 GB	1.6 GB	5 GB
Milano (52 nodes)	0.15 GB	1.1 GB	4.5 GB
MAN157 (157 nodes)	1.3 GB	2.1 GB	7.8 GB

As shown in **TABLE 3**, the simulation time increases significantly with the number of packets, particularly for larger topologies, and also depending on the number of hops between the ACOs and the MCOs. Similarly, RAM memory requirements grow with both the number of packets and the network size. **TABLE 4** highlights that the memory requirements for the MAN157 topology are high. These memory demands may exceed the capacity of a standard PC with 16 GB RAM when simulating a high number of packets on large topologies, posing challenges for simulations under these scenarios.

To address the limitations on memory requirements, a second version of the simulator was developed, and adapted to Google Colab environment³⁵. This version is optimized for the simulation of flows in parallel, enabling comparisons of memory versus runtime requirements as a function of the number of cores used.

To see how parallelization can be used, an experiment was conducted for 1,000 packets across the three topologies, and the results are presented in **FIGURE 4**. These show that it is possible to select an optimal number of cores to find a balance between runtime and memory demands. Nevertheless, when dealing with extremely complex network topologies and large-scale simulation packets, certain scenarios still present impractical time or memory requirements for users, especially in the context of real-time Digital Twin applications.

To resolve this issue, we have shown that the narrow VP upper bound can be used, as it offers an efficient theoretical alternative for estimating delay percentiles in such scenarios. We will validate its use on large topologies in the next section.

FIGURE 4 Comparison of Time and Memory Usage Performance for Optimized Code Using Different Number of Cores in 1000 Packets per Flow

3.5 | Fast evaluation of full topology with VP bound

In the next experiments, we aim to evaluate the goodness of fit of the VP bound on large MAN network topologies with different transmission capacity values (10 Gb/s, 40 Gb/s, 100 Gb/s, and 400 Gb/s) and link distances (network diameters between 2 and 20 Km). The results are shown in **FIGURES 5**, **6**, **7** for Milano, Tokyo, and MAN157 MANs respectively. The boxplots (left) of **FIGURE 5** for MilanNet, **FIGURE 6** for Tokyo⁵⁰, and **FIGURE 7** for MAN157 topology show both average delay (red boxplots) and 99-th percentiles (blue boxplots) including transmission, queuing, and propagation delays.

As shown, as link capacity increases (especially at 100G and 400G), the Vysochanskij–Petunin’s bound for the 99-th delay percentile gets closer to the average theoretical delay, showing that at high-transmission rates, queuing and transmission delay is almost negligible compared to propagation delay. This is especially true as the network diameter increases above 10 Km as shown in **FIGURES 6**, **5**, **7** (right). This conclusion makes sense since propagation contributes with 50 μs while a single packet transmission at 100 Gb/s is typically below 1 μs .

3.6 | Discussion and applicability

This section shows how to use the VP bound for estimating delay percentiles in any generic MAN topology. To do this, let us consider a MAN topology with 20 ACOs and 4 MCOs. The network operator aims to provide 300 μs MAN transport latency at most between every ACO and its closest MCO. On this topology, the ACO-MCO paths range between 5 and 20 Km and the number of hops is between 2 and 5 intermediate nodes. The network operator needs to check if 10 Gb/s capacity is sufficient to guarantee one-way latency below 300 μs or needs to migrate to 100 Gb/s link capacity.

Concerning propagation delay, packets will experience a fixed delay between 25 μs (for 5 Km links) and 100 μs for 20 Km links, regardless of link capacity, that is, propagation of light takes 5 μs per Km for silica fibers.

Concerning transmission delay, the average packet service time for traffic observed at the AMS-IX (i.e. 1019 Byte average packet size) is 0.81 μs at 10 Gb/s (or ten times less at 100 Gb/s, that is 0.081 μs).

For queuing delay, we consider a worst-case scenario where nodes operate at 90% of their capacity (i.e. $\rho = 0.9$ link load), thus queuing delay approaches an exponential distribution as it follows from the Kingman’s law of congestion. The average delay at 10 Gb/s can be then approximated by:

FIGURE 5 Boxplots for average queuing delay and 99-th percentile Vysochanskij-Petunin’s bound for the MAN network topology of Milano, (left) at 10 Gb/s, 40 Gb/s, 100 Gb/s, and 400 Gb/s, (right) at 100 Gb/s with different link distances with multiplicative factors 1x, 2x, 4x, and 10x

FIGURE 6 Boxplots for average queuing delay and 99-th percentile Vysochanskij-Petunin’s bound for the MAN network topology of Tokyo, (left) at 10 Gb/s, 40 Gb/s, 100 Gb/s, and 400 Gb/s, (right) at 100 Gb/s with different link distances with multiplicative factors 1x, 2x, 4x, and 10x

$$E(D_i) \approx E(X) \frac{1}{1 - \rho_i} = 0.815 \frac{1}{1 - 0.9} = 8.15 \mu s \quad (31)$$

FIGURE 7 Boxplots for average queuing delay and 99-th percentile Vysochanskij-Petunin's bound for the MAN network topology of MAN157, (left) at 10 Gb/s, 40 Gb/s, 100 Gb/s, and 400 Gb/s, (right) at 100 Gb/s with different link distances with multiplicative factors 1x, 2x, 4x, and 10x

Remark that both standard deviation and expectation have the same value for the exponential distribution, that is, $8.15 \mu\text{s}$. Thus, the average total delay for traversing N nodes at 90% load (worst-case) is $N \cdot E(D)$, that is, between $16.30 \mu\text{s}$ (for 2 hops) and $40.75 \mu\text{s}$ (for 5 hops). The standard deviation is $\sqrt{N}Sd(D)$, that is, between $11.5 \mu\text{s}$ (for 2 hops) and $18.22 \mu\text{s}$ (for 5 hops).

Finally, using the VP bound for high percentiles in the 5-hop scenario gives (eq. 20):

$$D_{.90} \leq \sqrt{\frac{4}{9} \frac{1}{1-0.9}} 18.22 \mu\text{s} + 40.75 \mu\text{s} = 79.16 \mu\text{s} \quad \text{all links at 10 Gb/s}$$

$$D_{.99} \leq \sqrt{\frac{4}{9} \frac{1}{1-0.99}} 18.22 \mu\text{s} + 40.75 \mu\text{s} = 162.22 \mu\text{s} \quad \text{all links at 10 Gb/s} \quad (32)$$

In conclusion, in the worst-case scenario including five intermediate hops heavily loaded $l = 0.9$ and maximum distance (20 Km), the VP bound guarantees that 99% of the packets will experience one-way delay below $262.22 \mu\text{s}$ ($100 \mu\text{s}$ for propagation and $162.22 \mu\text{s}$ for variable queuing plus transmission delay) for nodes operating at 10 Gb/s. Our simulator can find the real $D_{.99}$ percentile at $195.56 \mu\text{s}$ delay, which is below the $262.22 \mu\text{s}$ theoretical upper bound of Vysochanskij-Petunin.

Finally, at 100 Gb/s, the VP bound states that 99% of the packets will be below $115.92 \mu\text{s}$ ($100 \mu\text{s}$ for propagation and only $15.92 \mu\text{s}$ for transmission and queuing). Our simulator can find the real $D_{.99}$ percentile at $109.32 \mu\text{s}$ delay which is close but below the VP bound.

4 | SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND FUTURE WORK

This article introduces an open-source network simulator and digital twin specifically designed for Metropolitan Area Networks (MAN). The main objective of this tool is to estimate average latency and delay percentiles between node pairs, focusing on the capability of MANs to support emerging services with stringent latency requirements. The article demonstrates that employing probability bounds, such as the Vysochanskij-Petunin (VP) inequality, allows for accurate estimation of latency percentiles with minimal computational resources, especially as topology sizes grow in length (network diameter) and transmission capacity increases. The theoretical findings are substantiated through extensive simulations utilizing the *simmer* package, a discrete event simulator in R, alongside *igraph* for network visualization and shortest path calculations. The simulator is made available in two versions on GitHub: one for local PC execution and another optimized for cloud environments with enhanced processing power⁵³.

In general, this research not only presents a novel tool for simulating network delays but also contributes to the broader understanding of transport latency in MANs. The simulator's user-friendly interface allows easy input of topology information via spreadsheets, facilitating analysis and interpretation of results. By focusing on delay percentiles rather than just average latencies, the authors aim to ensure that a significant majority of packets meet stringent latency thresholds required by emerging applications. Both simulator and theoretical VP bound are validated using real Metro Network topologies (Tokyo, MilanNet, and MAN157) showing that the theoretical approach constitutes a good approximation to the actual simulated delay.

This theoretical approach can be used for different purposes, such as doing an initial evaluation of whether or not a given MAN can guarantee delay values below a given threshold. Indeed, the ability of a network to guarantee low and bounded delay percentiles is critical for moving toward the network envisioned by ITU-T FG2030, which demands faster networks with bounded latency for the upcoming services (autonomous vehicles, Industry Connected 4.0 and metaverse).

Future work will examine the usability and applicability of other tighter probabilistic bounds in larger scenarios than MANs, where transport capacity is above 100 Gb/s. With the advent of coherent pluggable transceivers operating at 400 Gb/s, 800 Gb/s, and even 1.6 and 3.2 Tb/s in the next years, we envision that queuing and transmission delay will be negligible at MANs and WANS, even for high delay percentiles. Also in subsequent future research, we plan to extend the simulator to incorporate the access segment, including wireless networks and PON architectures (including GPON and XGS-PON), in order to evaluate end-to-end performance across all segments of the network, including the potential delay implications of their MAC protocols.

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